

NGIoT Roadmap and Policy Recommendations

Strategy White Paper

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The European IoT Hub

Growing a sustainable and comprehensive ecosystem for Next Generation Internet of Things

**NEXT
GENERATION
IoT**

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AB	Advisory Board
AR	Artificial Reality
BEREC	Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CB	Coordination Board
CTF	Communication Task Force
DID	Decentralised Identifier
CB	Coordination Board
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CTF	Communication Task Force
DEI	Digitising European Industry
DEP	Digital Europe
DLTs	Distributed Ledger Technologies
EC	European Commission
ECUs	Electronic Control Units
EDPIA	European Digital Payments Industry Alliance
EG	Expert Groups
HPC	High-performance computing
HEP	Horizon Europe
IA	Innovation Actions
IAAS	Infrastructure-as-a-service
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
JU	Joint Undertaking
LEO	Low-Earth Orbit
MANO	Management and Orchestration
M2M	Machine to Machine
MR	Mixed Reality
NFV	Network Functions Virtualisation
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NGIOT	Next Generation Internet of Things
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OTA	Edge, over-the-air
RIA	Research and Innovation Actions
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDO	Standards Development Organization
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SoS	System of Systems
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TTN	The Things Network
UAVs	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
VR	Virtual Reality

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE

The goal of this paper is to provide an aligned view on the common strategic objectives across the European IoT ecosystem, linking to the relevant policies to provide tailored recommendations for mechanisms and structures to align policy objectives and technology development.

This document will first present an overview of the Next-generation Internet of Things, followed with a metadata review of the alignment of priorities within innovation and deployment from the IoT ecosystem with an analysis of the relevant legislations and policies.

The goal of this paper is not to replicate nor confuse the significant work already produced in this area and aims to fill the gaps in between.

This is a first version which provides the ground for future inputs from key experts and communities which will be captured in a second version to be published in March 2023 with updated legislations and strategic research agendas.

1.2 CONTEXT

EU-IoT is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) which coordinates a portfolio of projects funded under the Horizon 2020 ICT-56 'Next Generation Internet of Things' Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs). These RIAs are tasked with developing and trialling next-generation architectures that underpin the deployment and accelerated development of edge computing, distributed intelligence, federated microservices, collaborative IoT and tactile interfaces integrating holistically those enabling technologies such as DLTs and 5G.

These projects were awarded towards the end of the last Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Horizon 2020, as IoT has evolved from its relatively delineated field and scope to merge into the computing continuum from human to cloud. While the previous decade can be marked by the widescale adoption of cloud computing and the rise of the hyperscalers, behind much of the digital transformation, the next decade will see the rise of the edge and a distributed approach to data and intelligence.

The NGIoT Initiative is the stepping stone towards the Cloud-Edge-IoT paradigm which is being precipitated by the convergence of the cloud and edge. This is being driven by the increased computing power available on chips and devices and the realisation of the collaborative IoT enabled by 5G technologies. It is resulting in the processing of data closer to source with hyper local models and a models of models approach in cloud. Added to this is the move away from the screen internet where humans interact with devices in a myriad of ways, and are considered an active piece in the decision making to be taken by AI generating trust and confidence in the next generation of internet.

It may often appear that Europe has over the past decade found itself at a permanent 'cross-roads', from stimulating a resilient and competitive economy in response to the crises of the early 2010s, to adapting to a less stable world structures of the mid-late 2010s focus on 'digital sovereignty or self-reliance' to the current state of affairs which has brought a convergence of pandemic, climate, energy and territorial emergencies that requires a branch and root transformation to how European businesses and citizens operate and adjust to the 'digital and green transitions'.

With the advances achieved in digital technologies, Europe is now undergoing a legislative renewal with many aspects of digital technologies, services and markets being re-evaluated and regulated to reflect the change within which we find ourselves in a digital and societal context,

updating existing frameworks which have been designed for a screen-based internet world and adapting to the advances and shifts that the development and adoption of advanced digital technologies have brought about. This shift in multiple legislations in process at European level that have and will have a direct impact on shaping the future of the next-generation IoT in the Cloud-Edge-IoT Context.

Alongside this context is the launch of a set of policy instruments that have not been previously seen; Horizon Europe, Digital Europe and the Recovery and Resilience Fund combined and aligned together provides the strongest mechanisms available to the European Union ever to effect change in the digital technology market of Europe. A set of large bets to leapfrog Europe's global position and create a secure and reliable value chain for digital technologies from chips to data sovereignty to competitive platforms and edge solutions.

1.3 PRIOR READING

This document provides an overview of the intersection of policies and trends within the convergence of the Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) paradigm. Strategic roadmaps which cover the principal projections and priorities for research and innovation have recently been published and as such will not be duplicated here but will be complemented within the dynamic policy context. The outputs will link across these reports and guide practical recommendations for structures and mechanisms to support the achievement of the policy ambitions.

NGIoT: Roadmap for IoT Research, Innovation and Deployment in Europe 2021-2027¹

This White Paper covers a definition and key domains within IoT and Edge Computing, providing a sector vertical overview with an analysis of the opportunities, barriers, and communities within each domain (Agrifood, Smart Cities, Health, Energy, Manufacturing, Automotive). The NGIoT Roadmap provides a tech-based approach to key priorities and develops a series of recommendations in this area for Horizon Europe, Digital Europe and CEF 2 framework programmes.

Horizon CLOUD: Cloud Computing in Europe²

Horizon CLOUD takes a supply and demand approach to enabling the digital transformation through cloud adoption. It structures a set of recommendations around four key pillars of Data Aware Organisations, Data-driven Innovation, Strengthening the EU Market, and Foundational Elements. This is complemented by an earlier comprehensive strategy report which analyses and defines the major challenges facing cloud computing providers and adopters. It addresses in detail the demand domains of energy, transport, agriculture health and manufacturing with a specific approach to SMEs as well as addressing the supply side.³

¹ [IoT Research, Innovation and Deployment Priorities in the EU, White Paper, Version 2.0](#), (2022), Molina Castro F. *et al*, NGIoT CSA Consortium

² [Cloud Computing in Europe: Landscape Analysis, Adoption Challenges and Future Research and Innovation Opportunities, White Paper, Version 1.6](#), (2022), Dietrich M., Facca, F. *et al*, H-CLOUD CSA Consortium

³ [Strategy analysis report and Cloud Computing](#), (2021), Dietrich M. *et al*, H-CLOUD CSA Consortium

EU-IoT produced mapping and analysis

In addition to the above external reports, the EU-IoT consortium has already provided significant mapping and scoping reports and activities contained within the following documents:⁴

- D2.2 Towards a Vibrant EU IoT Ecosystem Version 2
 - Provides an overview of the NGIoT technology landscape, identifies key challenges within the principal framework areas and provides the definition of the NGIoT Community and actors.
- D2.3 Experts consultation and dialogues report Version 1
 - Reports on engagement with experts on the validation of the EU IoT framework approach with inputs on technology maturity, and market drivers.
- D3.5 Mapping of Knowledge Areas to Standardisation Version 1
 - Maps the principal technologies and knowledge areas from 3 strategic research and innovation agendas against Horizon Europe clusters and SDOs.
- D3.7 Recommendations on research priorities and innovation strategies to standardization Version 1
 - Presents the mapping of the key areas of standardisation and relevant bodies for the research and innovation activities across the ICT56 RIAs (NGIoT Initiative).

⁴ Publicly available through the NGIoT Portal: www.ngiot.eu/deliverables

2 THE NEXT GENERATION IOT

2.1 Overview

The exact definition of IoT has been attempted by various bodies, for example while the IEEE reached a definition based on a description of the constituent elements, the ITU provides a catch all definition which relies on what the IoT achieves. The colleagues have within the NGIoT Roadmap have surmised that the IoT is “a system of systems that have (at least) the following properties: Sensing and actuation, Connectivity, Intelligence, Heterogeneity, Dynamicity, Scalability, Security”.¹ At its most basic the IoT consists of a sensor which generates data that it communicates over a network to a central point for processing and abstraction of knowledge, but what differentiates the IoT from the NGIoT?

The Next-Generation IoT is characterised by a set of properties driven by the convergence of the edge and cloud and which includes (non-exhaustive):

- Federated architectures designed for distributed or swarm intelligence and federated services.
- Intelligent devices with hardware accelerators for on-device processing.
- The integration of microservices which support trust and security functions.
- Novel human-IoT interfaces such as AR and haptic responses.
- Leveraging of 5G management with network functional virtualisation and slicing.
- Management of public cloud and edge environments in the same application.

This is typified by the example meta- and high-level architecture of the IoT-NGIN RIA in the figure below.⁵

⁵ D1.2 IoT meta-architecture, components, and benchmarking, September 2021, IoT NGIN Consortium

Figure 1. Overview of the IoT NGIN meta-architecture (above) and high-level (below) demonstrating the integration of multiple technologies and microservices with novel and secure interfaces

2.2 Tech, Market, Skills and Standards on the Human to Cloud continuum

The European IoT landscape embraces several initiatives focusing on an increasing number of novel technologies across several verticals that allow for the proliferation of new IoT solutions and services models.

To properly understand and analyse the needs of such a diverse and ever-growing community, it is necessary to create a mapping process and a framework that allows EU-IoT to properly capture the core requirements and needs, despite the diversity, while considering the specificity of different cases. Staying agile and being able to capture needs in a fast-changing context is a major requirement that was accounted for within the EU-IoT project, when coming up with the framework that is proposed hereby.

The proposed EU-IoT framework operates along two axes, the first addresses the points of interaction between the physical elements which make up the human-to-cloud continuum, reflecting the current and future structure of the IoT. This axis looks at the human-device-gateway-networks-cloud points of engagement and identifies areas and themes of progress between and across them.

Figure 2. The IoT continuum - from human to cloud and back again with key interfaces

The second axis refers to five key research and innovation areas / technological phases which can overlap and have a reach across the continuum that EU-IoT will focus on: the Human/IoT interface, the Far Edge (devices level), the Near Edge (gateway level), the Infrastructure (including networks) and the Data Spaces. Within these five key areas/contexts, which bracket advances, discussions, and debates, EU-IoT addresses four broad main themes grouping important transversal aspects, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Guiding framework of the EU-IoT approach

These four main transversal dimensions focus on:

- Technology: to identify novel and advancing enabling technologies.
- Market: to identify applications, services, and models enabled by the technologies (both individual and varied combinations).
- Standards and policies: to elaborate on common approaches, standards, and policies.
- Skills: to analyse the current and future demands resulting from all the above.

Figure 4. Technology priorities in the NGIoT landscape, framework in action.

3 STRATEGIC TOPICS AND THEMES RELATED TO THE NGIOT

3.1 Summary of relevant Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas

Across the NGIoT domain there is a series of industry associations and research partnerships who develop and contribute towards a set of Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas (SRIAs). These agendas map out the upcoming trends and priorities for the industries and tech areas that they represent providing a strong guidance for their respective members, communities and policy makers for alignment of investments and actions. Some of this has already been addressed in the Deliverable 3.5 *Mapping of Knowledge Areas to Standardisation*⁶, which provides the individual mapping of the technology and knowledge areas towards the Horizon Europe Clusters.

Below is provided a meta-analysis of the key priority areas, technologies and applications found within public and relevant SRIAs to identify common themes and trends across the relevant communities for the NGIoT. These SRIAs include the following:

- Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda, AI, Data & Robotics Partnership, September 2020 (BDVA/DAIRO, CLAIRE, ELLIS, EurAI, EURobotics).
- European industrial technology roadmap for the next generation cloud-edge offering, May 2021, European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud.
- ECS: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2021 (Aeneas, Artemis-IA, EPoSS).
- MADE IN EUROPE: The manufacturing partnership in Horizon Europe Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, September 2021, (EFFRA).

The latest SRIA from AIOTI is in the final stages of preparation and will be later integrated into the second version of this document.⁷ This second version will revise the later versions of such documents produced across all associations and make a comparison to the current analysis to detect changes in directions, emerging themes, and relative importance.

3.2 Mapping within an NGIOT context

Within each of the SRIAs and associated documents the 146 isolated topics are refined into priority areas, applications and technologies which are addressed across all fields.

- Priority areas refer to topics of strategic importance which represent a high-level direction that encompasses multiple technologies and applications.
- Applications are specific implementations of technologies either within in a specific context or addressing a defined goal.
- Technologies are referred to within a standalone context and as an enabler of the above applications and priority areas.

Shown in the figure below, the topics within these categories can be placed within the EU-IoT framework to demonstrate trends and gaps within the current directions for the NG-IoT.

Due to the nature of the SRIAs and roadmaps, the topics are concentrated within the Tech layer at nearly double the number of topics related to Market with a further gap present between it and

⁶ D3.5 Mapping of Knowledge Areas to Standardisation Version 1; EU-IoT Consortium

⁷ A high-level review of the AIOTI key technology areas to be developed within this document can be found in the annex to Deliverable D3.5 and has been included here.

Standards. As was also observed from the road mapping performed of the NGIoT (D2.2) and expert engagement, Skills is rarely addressed and presents again a significant weakness in the development of the NGIoT with only a single reference across the nearly 150 isolated topics.

The Far Edge is the phase of most interest representing 32% of all topics, this is followed by those which address the whole breadth, All with 21%. Human Interfaces is close behind with 17%, still at nearly half of the Far Edge. Data Spaces comes further behind with a relatively similar distribution between Infrastructure and Near Edge (8% and 6% respectively). 6% of topics are found within Other capturing those which do not fit easily within this framework.

Figure 5. Distribution of all topics within the relevant SRIAs mapped within the EU IoT framework

The priority areas are principally addressing the Tech development within the Far Edge, followed by the Human Interface and Market areas across All phases and the development of standards within the Data Spaces. Auspicious is the lack of priority areas addressing the Near Edge with focus now appearing to be much closer to the device and the human engagement with it.

The Near Edge appears to be underrepresented within this mapping, while the Far Edge was defined for topics that were on-device, the presence and discussion of topics related to edge nodes and gateways was not fully evident with broad topics (considered ALL) addressing relevant areas for the Near Edge. However, when a secondary phase (Figure 6 along the x-axis) is identified for a topic, it can be seen that there is clustering between the Near Edge and Far Edge with smaller links to the Human Interface and Far Edge.

Figure 6. Contour map showing the links between a primary categorisation and secondary where a topic touches upon two phases

When looking at the applications, it was expected that the majority would be within the Market layer, however, the majority are referring to the application of the technology or group of technologies to achieve a goal but not within a business or specific context. The top applications are centred within the Far Edge and across All Phases with little engagement within Infrastructure and the disappearance of skills. Concentrations are present within the tech for the Human Interfaces, Far Edge and All (6, 8, and 8 topics respectively) and for the Market applications within All (4 topics). The application of standards with Far Edge is distinct to the priority areas with also Near Edge and Data Spaces tech applications making an appearance.

The dominance of the Far Edge within specific technologies is returned with a minor emphasis on Infrastructure closely followed by the Human Interface. Some of the defined technologies have a targeted market application (e.g., allergen sensing) but in the main it is the Tech layer represented.

Figure 7. Distribution of all topics within the EU-IoT Framework by type

Overall, it can be seen that the latest SRIAs show a definitive shift towards the far edge, with a large emphasis on the development of new components and the creation of a network of intelligent devices. Resulting from the tech developer community, this push of tech development shows a clear understanding of the desire to enable the next-generation of Cloud-Edge-IoT but is uneven across the whole field, with a need to provide tech emphasis to enable the federated cloud and data spaces, an updated role for the near edge and the need for stronger market focus on the demand for the different technologies across key sectors as provided by the NGIoT Roadmap (See Section 1.3).

Despite expectations, the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership is much more focused on the Human Interface and Far Edge compared to the Data Spaces and Near Edge, the ECS alliance is in line with component and broad engineering focus within the Far Edge and All respectively while the provisional priority areas for AIOTI are evenly addressing the whole NGIoT.

	HUMAN INTERFACE	FAR EDGE	NEAR EDGE	INFRA STRUCTURE	DATA SPACES	ALL	OTHER
AI, Data and Robotics Partnership	18	19	1		1	3	
AIOTI	2	1	1	2		4	
ECS	2	18	1	5	2	13	4
European Alliance for Industrial Cloud Edge		5	2	3	7	1	2
EFFRA	3	4	3	2	5	9	3

Figure 8. Relative distribution of all topics within individual SRIAs using non-normalised data

3.3 Key themes identified

Across all the SRIAs, the common themes arise which define the current trajectories and priorities for technology development. Principal across these are the overriding fields of improving human-device interfaces and developing trust, however, with a significant introduction and emphasis on sustainability and the achievement of low-power and efficient devices at each point within the system of systems.

As can be seen in the Figure 9, the largest theme is contextual IoT, this relates to topics which seek to address the application of IoT within constrained environments for trustworthy, relevant and autonomous/semi-autonomous decision-making. The topics address the operation with domain-specific models, adaptation to changes within the environment, planning for and dealing with uncertainty and complex natural environments and the integration of multi-agent and human inputs. The major contributor to this theme is the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership who provide almost all the topics within this theme reflecting the previous emphasis on the Human-IoT Interfaces and Far Edge.

Figure 9. Key themes present across SRIAs by number of associated topics

Sustainability is well represented across the themes, with a strong contribution from the ECS, followed by the Industrial Cloud-Edge-IoT Alliance and EFFRA. The theme addresses the development of a technology stack that is itself sustainable by design with planning for extended lifetime operation through mechanisms for achieving reduced obsolescence, recyclability of the components and the application of the technology towards decarbonisation and energy consumption of industries.

Interoperability, while implicit in other themes such as contextual IoT, sustainability, legacy integration and data sharing is third in scale as an explicit stand alone and refers to the modular design concept of software and platforms within an SoS context and constrained environments. It is seen as a key lever for the scalability of the developed technologies and management of performance of the system as a whole within platforms with established standards and engineering approaches to facilitate whole value chain adoption.

As an individual technology group, AI is well represented within the context of ensuring the trustworthiness, which is composed of the preservation of security, privacy, zero-trust identification management and *explainability* of the decisions. The element of trust is also present within the theme of contextual IoT⁸ and reliability, the latter which addresses the robustness of the system as a whole compared to just the AI element.

THEME	AI, Data, Robotics	AIOTI	ECS	Cloud Alliance	EFFRA
CONTEXTUAL IOT	84%		4%		12%
SUSTAINABILITY	6%		50%	22%	22%
INTEROPERABILITY	6%	6%	47%	6%	35%
TRUSTWORTHY AI	50%	7%	21%	14%	7%
ENERGY/POWER	8%	8%	50%	33%	
COMPONENTS		20%	40%	10%	30%
FOUNDATIONAL TECH		11%	44%	33%	11%
NOVEL SENSORS	56%		11%	11%	22%
RELIABILITY	11%	33%	33%	11%	11%
MARKET				50%	50%
INTERFACES	75%	25%			
ADOPTABILITY	50%				50%
LEGACY INTEGRATION			100%		
DATA SHARING			33%		67%
OTHER			67%		33%

Figure 10. Relative distribution of themes by source using non-normalised data

Coming through clearly is also a demand for low power consumption within sensors and devices approaching even zero energy systems. The goals are to balance power and performance towards performance and reducing the energy footprint of the systems including better thermal management and achieving efficient HPC. It is a key priority for the component and cloud communities with a definition of the required technologies rather than applications.

The development of next-generation components and specifically sensors is a drive across the communities. Components refer more to software and middleware to support the integration of

⁸ This overlap of topics across these two themes may be related to the difference in terminology and priorities between the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership and the ECS cooperation.

the devices to the cloud and the rolling out of novel AI accelerations with a flexible system of cloud and edge computing. Novel sensors are required that are wearable, self-configuring and contributing to heterogenic data sets, with a new class of chemical and bio-based sensors which can accurately identify and quantify small-molecules on a picomolar scale.

Behind all these themes is the requirement for more foundational technology development which covers advanced radio frequencies and photonics (infrastructure), silicon technologies and wafer fabrication (devices), quantum computing (HPC) and satellite IoT as both communications and acting as an edge-node.

Other topics of note include specific business case driven applications, methods for reducing the barriers to adoption and the virtualisation of legacy systems and integration of existing embedded systems within the NGIoT systems.

Notably absent from the above themes are those topics related to orchestration and container-based solutions for migrating applications to the edge with context awareness, flexible networks for a programmable, multi-purpose general infrastructure through network virtualisation, resilient microservices architecture beyond REST and AI/ML-as-a-Service for a prosumer approach to edge-AI. These topics are dealt with in detail within the NetWorld2020 SRIA⁹ led by the previous 5G-PPP and are currently being addressed by the ICT 56 RIAs which form the NGIoT Initiative and are present in the road mapping conducted in D2.1 and D2.2 EU-IoT deliverables.

⁹ Smart Networks in the context of NGI, September 2020, European Technology Platform NetWorld2020

4 POLICY ANALYSIS

4.1 A new age for Digital Policy development

The past decade has been one in which European political leaders have navigated a myriad of societal and economic challenges, requiring policy measures that support the emergence of a more resilient and competitive economy and prepare Europe to deal with a less stable global political environment.

The convergence of pandemic, climate, energy and territorial emergencies has required a branch and root transformation of how European businesses and citizens operate and adjust to the digital and green transitions. Ensuring Europe’s digital “sovereignty” that has become a fundamental part of ensuring future competitiveness and underpinning social freedom.

Throughout this period, the pace of technological development has accelerated and policy making now, more than ever, must be based a forward-looking approach that takes into account how data and technology usage will evolve in the near and more distant future. In the view of the European Agency for Fundamental Human Rights, “Using AI systems engages a wide range of fundamental rights, regardless of the field of application. These include – but also go beyond – privacy, data protection, non-discrimination and access to justice.”¹⁰

4.2 Driving recovery and resilience through a Single Digital Market

Across Europe, policy discussions, initiatives and regulations are underway, updating existing regulatory and normative frameworks, and adapting them to the all-pervasive digital economy that is shaping society and business and even politics. Many of them will have a direct impact on the future of the next-generation IoT and the move to the Cloud-Edge-IoT paradigm.

Figure 11. Quantifying Spillovers of Next Generation EU Investment, Discussion Paper July 2021. European Commission.

¹⁰ Getting the future right. Artificial intelligence and fundamental rights. FRA. 2020.

The deployment of the Recovery and Resilience Fund, a temporary recovery instrument that made available a total of €723.8 billion¹¹ in loans (€385.8 billion) and grants (€338 billion) to Member States to implement reforms and new initiatives aligned with EU priorities around climate change and the digital transition, has increased the importance of reviewing the policies and instruments that regulate the digital and data economy for consumers/citizens and businesses.

To date, Member States¹² have allocated close to 40% of spending to climate measures and more than 26% on the digital transition, exceeding the respective targets of 37% and 20%, with significant cross-border spillover effects that highlight the financial benefits of pursuing a single digital market.

4.3 Overview of main regulations to guide the NG-IoT

The effective functioning of the Single Digital Market relies on the availability of a harmonised regulatory¹³ framework that can protect rights, and provide guidance and legal certainty to all stakeholders. From this perspective, the most relevant policy initiatives include a set of proposed regulations that are complementary in scope and objective:

- Proposal for Data Act {SEC (2022) 81 final}
- Data Governance Act {SEC(2020) 405 final}
- Proposal for Digital Markets Act {SEC(2020) 437 final}
- Proposal for Digital Services Act {SEC(2020) 432 final}
- Proposal for Artificial Intelligence Act {SEC(2021) 167 final}
- Proposal for a Chips Act (2022) (pending review)

Figure 12. Main regulations that are likely to have a direct impact on the NG-IoT

Each of these confers a distinct set of rights and obligation on different stakeholders in the digital ecosystem, seeking to clarify what can and cannot be done with data in a range of settings. The paragraphs that follow offer a brief description of the proposals as they stand. There is also another set of policies that are related, such as the Data Governance Act, which in the

¹¹ In current prices.

¹² Across 22 recovery and resilience plans approved so far

¹³ A "regulation" is a directly applicable form of EU law, which has binding legal force in all member states. National governments do not have to take action to implement EU regulations. A "directive" is a legislative act setting a goal to be achieved by all EU countries, but leaving the method to each member state.

performance of this study of this context has unveiled the complexity of the space within which the NGIoT and the Cloud-Edge-IoT domain operates and warrants a further cross-legislative analysis.

4.3.1 Data Act

Scope

The proposed Data Act relates to the sharing non-personal data that is generated through the use of connected product or related service by a user from the data holder to the user or a designated third-party data processor authorised by the user.

The data covered within the proposed regulation includes:

- Data in the form and format that is generated by the product.
- Data from related services that are bundled, including that not provided by the manufacturer but a third party.
- Data arising from the use Virtual Assistants.

The regulation holds four main areas:

- B2B and B2C data sharing and access
 - Providing timely and continuous access to the data that is easily, securely and where possible, directly accessed by the user or their authorised third party at the same standard to which the data holder has access.
- Provision of data to public bodies for an *exceptional need*
 - Provided free-of-charge when requested as part of a response to a public emergency.
 - Provided at cost plus reasonable margin when requested to prevent or recover from a public emergency or to overcome a barrier in completing a task in the public interest.
- Portability of digital assets from cloud and edge platforms (data processing services)
 - Ensuring that platform customers can switch between providers and on-premises servers within 30 days with continuity of service and provision of functions and assist the switching process to completion.
 - Obliging data processing services to port all data assets which includes data, applications, virtualised machines, etc.
 - Provide a detailed report and alternative solutions where portability is not technically unfeasible.
- Interoperability mechanisms and standards
 - Definition of obligations for the operators of data spaces with regards to data record and access
 - Definition of the essential requirements for smart contract (and their operators) which facilitate the management of the data sharing.
 - Provide the Commission with the capacity to request and enforce interoperability standards for data spaces, cloud interoperability and smart contract interoperability for the definition of compliance with the requirements and obligations.

Description

The proposed regulation aims to establish a legislative mechanism for ensuring the fairness and access to data by the persons (legal or natural) who generates it through their use of a purchased device or physical item that has connectivity, and associated service, as well as strengthening the access by government bodies to essential data for exceptional need. It aims to release data for the development of new services on top of devices and data, enable the portability across data service providers (e.g., cloud and edge platforms), support public bodies to respond to crises and societal challenges.

Under the proposed legislation, upon request by the user or consumer, the data holder (device manufacturer, lessor or other) is required to provide access in a useable, continuous and real-time format for the execution of a specific purpose.

This will require data holders (device manufacturers and service providers) to design their products and services in such a way that individual user data can be isolated, treated to remove any personal data (when required) and made accessible for the user or a designated third-party. Data holders are able to charge reasonably for these services to cover the investment made but must be provided at cost to SMEs; in either case it will have to provide a break down for how this compensation was calculated.

It also requires an adjustment to the purchase, leasing or renting agreements to clearly define how data is generated, used and made accessible. Across the Data Act, it is intended to provide protection to SMEs by ensuring fair terms of agreement within data sharing contracts through the application of an unfairness test. The Commission will also be charged with providing model contractual terms for data sharing contracts to support the evaluation and negotiation of such agreements. The *sui genesis* claim (i.e. the investment in the creation of a database was significant and should be protected) under the Directive on the Legal Protection of Databases does not apply – cannot be used as a reason for denying access to user-generated data.

For the operator of cloud and edge platforms, the act creates a significant set of obligations to enable the switching and multi-vendor environment for users through the portability of the assets and the establishment of the responsibility towards ensuring ‘*functional equivalence*’ when switching to a comparable service. It requires the platform providers to develop the mechanisms to facilitate this and to provide the interfaces and adhere to interoperability standards and the responsibility to ensure the security and integrity of the data.

The regulation defines the roles and responsibilities of operators of data spaces to ensure compliance with the data sharing requirements including the relevant documentation and technical interfaces for automatic and continuous data transition and the minimum requirements for robust smart contracts (such as an emergency stop and rest button) as both are seen to be enablers for the execution of the actions within the regulation.

Consequently, the NGIoT stakeholders will be required to consider the design of their systems and architectures to provide the necessary functions and develop the data interfaces with secure authentication that will be required to put the regulation into action. Existing data will need to be mapped and sliced based on users for traceability and compliance with requests. It will drive the development of interoperability standards within cloud computing to overcome the current technical incompatibility preventing portability in practice and drive the definition of the smart contracts to facilitate the authenticated and controlled sharing between parties.

Key challenges will exist among the data holders who will have a commercial interest in retaining data and for cloud providers to be able to provide the necessary portability due to the current misalignment between the principal hyperscale platforms. The ‘minimum functionality’ must be maintained and suitable standards and approaches will be required to define this minimum functionality and switching capacity from a technical point of view. The Commission may drive this through ETSI or similar.

Stakeholders

- Business users, consumers, data holders (device manufacturers or service providers), data processing service providers, third party data processors (supplier to user and supplier to manufacturer or service provider), public bodies.

Main exclusions

- Data inferred or derived from usage of the product or service.
- Data from the use of mobile phones and tablets.
- Personal data; must be requested through a data controller or subject as under GDPR.
- Gatekeepers who are designated under the Digital Markets Act do not have the rights to access or process the data within this regulation.
- Request for data by public bodies as part of activities related to criminal offences, customs and taxation administration, and where the data can already be obtained on the market.
- Disclosure of trade secrets; except where necessary for the execution with agreements in place to ensure confidentiality.
- Proprietary data and IPR belonging to the data holder.
- Sector-specific needs within data sharing.

Specific exclusions for small and micro enterprises, these organisations are:

- Not required to comply with design obligations except where it is a sub-contractor for the design and manufacture of a product.
- Exempt from the obligations related to the sharing of data generated by the use of their products or related services
- Not required to comply with data requests from public authorities.

4.3.2 Proposal for a Digital Markets Act

Scope

It applies to core platform services provided or offered by gatekeepers to business users established in the Union or end users established or located in the Union, irrespective of the place of establishment or residence of the gatekeepers and of other law otherwise applicable to the provision of service.

Description

The proposed regulation lays down harmonised rules ensuring contestable and fair markets in the digital sector across the Union where gatekeepers are present. It applies to core platform services provided or offered by gatekeepers to business users. Core platform services means any of the following:

- online intermediation services;
- online search engines;
- online social networking services;
- video-sharing platform services;
- number-independent interpersonal communication services
- operating systems;
- cloud computing services;
- advertising services, including any advertising networks, advertising exchanges and any other advertising intermediation services, provided by a provider of any of the above.

At the heart of the regulation is the figure of the **Gatekeeper**, a provider of core platform services that has a significant impact on the internal market, operates a core platform service which serves as an important gateway for business users to reach end users, and enjoys an entrenched and durable position in its operations or it is foreseeable that it will enjoy such a position in the near future.

Stakeholders

Gatekeepers, competitors, business users, consumers, regulatory authorities.

Main exclusions

Electronic communications networks and electronic communications services.¹⁴

4.3.3 Proposal for a Digital Services Act

Description

The Regulation aims to contribute to the proper functioning of the internal market for intermediary services and set out uniform rules for a safe, predictable and trusted online environment, to protect fundamental human rights.

Scope

It applies to intermediary services provided to recipients of the service who are established or resident in the Union, irrespective of the place of establishment of the service providers.

¹⁴ As defined in point (1) of Article 2 of Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council, as defined in point (4) of Article 2 of Directive (EU) 2018/1972 other than those related to interpersonal communication services as defined in point (4)(b) of Article 2 of that Directive

Tailored asymmetric obligations

	Intermediary services	Hosting services	Online platforms	Very large platforms
Transparency reporting	√	√	√	√
Requirements on terms of service due account of fundamental rights	√	√	√	√
Cooperation with national authorities following orders	√	√	√	√
Points of contact and, where necessary, legal representative	√	√	√	√
Notice and action and obligation to provide information to users		√	√	√
Reporting criminal offences		√	√	√
Complaint and redress mechanism and out of court dispute settlement			√	√
Trusted flaggers			√	√
Measures against abusive notices and counter-notices			√	√
Special obligations for marketplaces, e.g. vetting credentials of third party suppliers ("KYBC"), compliance by design, random checks			√	√
Bans on targeted adverts to children and those based on special characteristics of users			√	√
Transparency of recommender systems			√	√
User-facing transparency of online advertising			√	√
Risk management obligations and crisis response				√
External and independent auditing, internal compliance function and public accountability				√
User choice not to have recommendations based on profiling				√
Data sharing with authorities and researchers				√
Codes of conduct				√
Crisis response cooperation				√

Source: [Europe fit for the Digital Age: new online rules for platforms](#). Accessed 26th April 2022.

Stakeholders

Intermediary service providers, recipients of the intermediary service.

Main exclusions

Some exclusions intermediary services that are known as “mere conduit”, “caching” and “hosting” services and for micro and small enterprises.

4.3.4 Proposal for an Artificial Intelligence Act

Description

The AI Act aims to provide clarity around what can and cannot be done with artificial intelligence in the European Union. It established harmonised rules for the placing and using AI on the market, and prohibits certain practices. It outlines specific requirements for high-risk AI systems and obligations for operators of such systems.

It also provides harmonised transparency rules for AI systems intended to interact with natural persons, emotion recognition systems and biometric categorisation systems, and AI systems used to generate or manipulate image, audio or video content. Finally, it set out the rules on market monitoring and surveillance.

An ‘artificial intelligence system’ (AI system) means software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I and can generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments with which they interact

A ‘provider’ means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body that develops an AI system or that has an AI system developed with a view to placing it on the market or putting it into service under its own name or trademark, whether for payment or free of charge.

Stakeholders

Providers of AI systems in the EU; users of AI systems located within the Union; providers and users of AI systems that are located in a third country, where the output produced by the system is used in the Union. Subjects of AI systems.

Main exclusions

AI systems developed or used exclusively for military purposes; AI used by public authorities in a third country or international organisations in the framework of international agreements or for law enforcement and judicial cooperation with the Union or with one or more Member States.

4.4 Relevance for NG-IoT stakeholders

4.4.1 Control-v-enable

The proposed regulations are different in scope and reach. Some impose tighter responsibilities on large online platforms to protect the fundamental rights of citizens. These regulations could be considered to address known problems that have already arisen through market dominance of a few players, controlling risks Others might be seen in a more forward looking light, seeking to enable innovation by providing legal certainty and a future-proof framework for operation:

4.4.2 Impact on the NG-IoT

The table below summarises the salient rights and obligations that may have an impact on NG-IoT stakeholders

Purpose	Main obligations
Data Act	
Ensuring that the user is able to make use of their generated data and stimulate innovation based data and deliver choice and	Data Holders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide users with timely access to data resulting from the use of the product or related service. • Make data available under fair, reasonable and non-discriminate terms in a transparent manner.

<p>autonomy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Make the data available to the same level as available to themselves (completeness, accuracy, reliability, up-to-date). ● Make data available to public bodies under an established exceptional need. ● Provide SMEs with the data at cost price for making the data available. ● Provide information of how data can be accessed within contract, leasing or purchase agreements. ● Provide description of the data generated, who will process and use it within contract, leasing or purchase agreements ● Provide a breakdown of costs of supply of data when charging data user. <p>They must not</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Impose unfair contractual terms on SMEs. ● Use any data from use of product or service to derive economic status or production methods to undermine the commercial position of the user. i.e. use own data against them commercially either directly or indirectly.
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<p>To prevent vendor lock-in with cloud and edge providers due to technical incapacity for switching limiting market growth and innovation.</p>	<p>Data Processing Service Providers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Port all digital assets of the customers – data, applications, virtual machines, etc. ● Provide necessary support for successful completion switching. ● Ensure, that where applications or similar cannot be ported, that the customer achieves functional equivalence of the new service. ● Prevent access to systems through robust cybersecurity practices. ● Provide open interfaces for data processing services that are not tied to their infrastructure ● Ensure compatibility with defined interoperability standard or provide the data in a structured, commonly used format
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Digital Markets Act

<p>To end unfair restrictions imposed by large-scale platforms, including cloud</p>	<p>Inter alia¹⁵, Gatekeepers must:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide effective portability of data. ● Provide business users or third parties authorised by them
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¹⁵ Key points. Full obligations are set out in articles 5 and 6 of the proposed regulation.

<p>computing platforms, to reduce lock-in effects and increase innovation.</p>	<p>with effective, high-quality, real time, continuous access to aggregated or non-aggregated data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide access to personal data only when this is directly connected to the use. ● Allow businesses to offer services outside the core platform on different terms. ● Impose the use of the gatekeeper’s own identification services own platform on business service users own offering. ● Provide advertisers and publishers with data on the performance of ads. <p>They must not:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technically restrict the ability of users to switch to other applications and services using the OS of the gatekeeper. ● Combine personal data sourced from the core platform services with any other personal data from services offered by them or data from third-party services. ● Automatically opt in end-users to additional services offered by them. ● Rank their own services above those of other business user.
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Digital Services Act

<p>Sets out obligations on intermediary information society services to ensure the proper functioning of the internal market and a safe, predictable and trusted online environment in which the fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter are duly protected</p>	<p>It includes obligations on intermediary service providers, including online platforms, in respect of setting up single points of contact in the EU and due diligence obligations for online safety and transparency including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing information on any restrictions on the use of their service, including information on any “...policies, procedures, measures and tools used for the purpose of content moderation, including algorithmic decision-making and human review.” ● Annual reports on content moderation. ● Mechanisms to allow “any individual or entity to notify them of the presence on their service of specific items of information that the individual or entity considers to be illegal content”. ● Prompt notification of suspicion of serious criminal offence involving threat to life or safety of persons. ● Provision of reasons for any detection, identification, removal or disabling of access to content. ● Establishment of systems to promptly act on notices submitted by trusted flaggers. ● Obligation to collect information on traders offering products
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or services to EU consumers and to provide an online interface that facilitates compliance with pre-contractual obligations and product safety information

- Transparency on advertising.

Additional obligations are placed on very large online platforms which serve more than 45 million monthly active recipients in the Union.

Artificial Intelligence Act

Proposes a single future-proof definition of AI and sets harmonised rules for the development, placement on the market and use of AI systems in the Union following a proportionate risk-based approach.

Prohibited artificial intelligence practices include systems or services that, inter alia:

- Use subliminal techniques to materially distort a person’s behaviour in a manner that could cause physical or psychological harm.
- Evaluate or classify of the trustworthiness of natural persons based on their social behaviour or known or predicted personal or personality characteristics, that can lead to detrimental or unfavourable treatment of people or groups in social contexts which are unrelated to the contexts in which the data was originally generated or collected or is unjustified or disproportionate to their social behaviour or its gravity.
- Use of real-time remote biometric identification system other than in the instances expressly allowed.

Amongst other obligations, high-risk AI systems¹⁶ require establishing, implementing and documenting a risk management system that:

- Identifies and analyses the known and foreseeable risks associated with each high-risk AI system.
- Estimates and evaluates the risks that may emerge when the high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose and under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse.
- Evaluates other possibly arising risks based on the analysis of data gathered from the post-market monitoring system (Art 61).
- Adopts suitable risk management measures in accordance with the provisions of the following paragraphs.

In addition:

- In eliminating or reducing risks related to the use of the high-risk AI system, the user’s technical knowledge, experience, education, training and the environment in

¹⁶ Defined in Art. 6

	<p>which the system is intended to be used must be taken into account.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tests should enable the most appropriate risk management measures to be identified, ensuring the system’s consistent performance and compliance. • The tests must be performed pre-market placement against pre-defined metrics, and suitable to achieve the intended purpose of the AI system but do not need to go beyond this. <p>In relation to the data and data governance, high-risk AI systems which make use of techniques involving the training of models with data shall be developed on the basis of training, validation and testing data sets that meet the quality criteria referred to in paragraphs 2 to 5 of Art. 10.</p> <p>Personal data may be processed to ensure bias monitoring provided state of the art security and privacy-preserving measure are introduced.</p> <p>Other important provisions include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The obligation to draw up technical documentation before the system is placed on the market. • Automatic recording of events (‘logs’) while the AI system is operating. • Ensuring sufficient transparency. • Incorporating human-machine interface tools to enable natural persons to oversee the AI system when it is in use. • Providers must affix the CE marking to indicate conformity. <p>It also provides for voluntary Codes of Conduct that will include requirements in relation to environmental sustainability, accessibility, stakeholder participation in design and development, diversity in development teams etc.</p>
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It is also worth noting that the proposed regulations impact on the different NG-IoT building blocks to differing degrees. The following figures provides a high-level indication of where each of the preceding regulations has the greatest relevance:

Figure 13. Mapping relevant regulation onto the NG-IoT

4.5 Key figures and compliance

4.5.1 Defining key roles

Regulation	Key Figure	Definition
Data Act	Data Holder	The manufacturer of a connected product or related service provider who receives the data generated from the use of the product or service that is put into the Single Market.
	Data Processing Service Provider	Providers of on-demand administration and broad remote access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources of a centralised, distributed or highly distributed nature which includes cloud or edge computing platform providers but not content platform providers.
Digital Markets Act	Gatekeeper	A provider of core platform services that has a significant impact on the internal market, operates a core platform service which serves as an important gateway for business users to reach end users and enjoys an entrenched and durable position in its operations or it is foreseeable that it will enjoy such a position in the near future.
Digital Services Act	Digital Services Coordinator	Member States shall designate one of the competent authorities as their Digital Services Coordinator, responsible for all matters relating to application and enforcement of this Regulation in that Member State, unless certain specific tasks or sectors have been assigned to other competent authorities.
	Trusted Flagger	Status awarded by the Digital Services Coordinators to entities that: (a) are expert and competent in detecting, identifying and notifying illegal content;

Regulation	Key Figure	Definition
		(b) represents collective interests and is independent from any online platform; (c) carries out its activities for the purposes of submitting notices in a timely, diligent and objective manner.
Artificial Intelligence Act	AI providers	Providers placing on the market or putting into service AI systems in the Union, irrespective of whether those providers are established within the Union or in a third country.
	High-risk AI systems	Where the AI system is intended to be used as a safety component of a product, or is itself a product, covered by the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex II; or the product whose safety component is the AI system, or the AI system itself as a product, is required to undergo a third-party conformity assessment with a view to the placing on the market or putting into service of that product pursuant to the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex II; or any system in Annex III.

4.5.2 The cost of non-compliance

The architectures, applications and data that stem from NG-IoT must be developed in a way that is compliant, as well as competitive. The table below provides a high-level of summary of the of the principal penalties for breach of the provisions in the regulations:

Instrument	Principal penalties for non-compliance
Data Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fines up to 20 000 000 EUR, or up to 4% of the total worldwide annual turnover of the preceding financial year, whichever is higher. Fines of up to 50 000 EUR per infringement and up to a total of 500 000 EUR per year for non-compliance with public bodies requests.
Digital Markets Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fines of up to 10% of the company’s total worldwide annual turnover, or up to 20% in the event of repeated infringements. Periodic penalty payments of up to 5% of the average daily turnover. After a market investigation additional proportionate penalties may be imposed.

Instrument	Principal penalties for non-compliance
Digital Services Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fines imposed on very large platforms found to be in breach of the regulation vary between 1-6% of total turnover in the preceding year.
Artificial Intelligence Act	<p>Market surveillance authorities are responsible for supervising and enforcing the rights and obligations. Where it has sufficient reason to believe an AI system presents a risk to health and safety or fundamental rights, it must carry out an evaluation. Where non-compliance has been established, the operator must take corrective action throughout the Union, which may involve withdrawal or recall.</p> <p>Penalties must be effective, proportionate and dissuasive, taking into account the interests of small scale providers and startups and their viability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-compliance with Art 5 & 10: 30 M EUR or 6% of total worldwide turnover. • Non-compliance with other provisions: 20 M EUR or 4% of total worldwide turnover. • Incorrect or misleading information: 10M EUR or 2% of total worldwide turnover. <p>Fines may also be imposed on Union institutions, agencies and bodies (art. 72).</p>

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

The policy landscape is far from static, with significant regulations still requiring the final seals of approval by the Union’s legislative bodies. Once approved, certain regulations, such as the AI Act, will still be subject to amendment on regular basis to allow for the rapid evolution of technology and the cases in which its design, deployment and use must be subject to regulatory oversight.

As things stands, and without prejudice to the need to seek professional legal advice, some of the recommendations to support compliance in the CEI large scale-pilots, as well as the open calls that invite new stakeholders into the pilots with a view to favouring ongoing innovation and exploration of new technological applications.

With this in mind, the recommendations below relate to:

- The rights that will be conferred by the new proposals and that may give access to interesting resources and capabilities
- The obligations that will come into force and that should be taken into account at the earliest possible stage in the process of designing and testing the architectures
- Supporting measures that may be implemented by the CSAs to explore both rights and obligations in the practical setting of the CEI large scale-pilots.

Accessing new resources and capabilities

1. FREEDOM TO OFFER SERVICES TO END USERS ACQUIRED THROUGH THE USE OF A CORE PLATFORM SERVICE

Under the proposed Digital Markets Act, business users may offer new services to end users acquired through the core platform services, independently of that platform.

2. CORE PLATFORM SERVICE DATA PORTABILITY

A business user may require that core platform services that are considered to be gatekeepers (including online intermediation services, online search engines, operating systems and cloud computing services, amongst others) ensures that their data is effectively portable. This will in theory help business users to avoid vendor lock-in and migrate to alternative providers.

3. FREEDOM TO ACCESS & AGGREGATE DATA FROM THE USE OF THE CORE PLATFORM SERVICE

They may also install third-party applications and “provide business users, or third parties authorised by a business user, free of charge, with effective, high-quality, continuous and real-time access and use of aggregated or non-aggregated data, that is provided for or generated in the context of the use of the relevant core platform services by those business users and the end users engaging with the products or services provided by those business users.”¹⁷

¹⁷ Different conditions apply to personal data, the use of which must be permissioned.

4. CAPACITY TO DEMONSTRATE ADDED-VALUE SERVICES THROUGH STARTUP AND SME ENGAGEMENT

The flow of non-personal data will launch a secondary market of data processors who can develop value-added services on top of connected products. A demonstration of this value is possible through the development of common data spaces within each of the large-scale pilots. These data environments will provide the ground upon which a set of proof-of-value experiments are able to be deployed with the additional inclusion of SMEs and startups through a set of open calls who can provide novel services through access to large databases, as has been shown with earth observation data under the previous framework programme with the European Space Agency. It will prove real evidence of commercially viable solutions to be realised within policy objectives and demonstrate the technical capacity for third party access and development.

Built-in compliance

1. OBLIGATION ON CORE PLATFORM SERVICE TO ENSURE DATA PORTABILITY

Providers of “core platform services”, which includes providers of operating systems and cloud computing services that have a significant impact¹⁸ on the internal market. If any stakeholder could be classified as a gatekeeper under the proposed Digital Markets Act, they must comply with the stipulations outlined in article 5 which prohibit certain practices in respect of user data and require them to ensure that their end or business user’s data is effectively portable.

This is further reinforced within the Data Act for cloud and edge platform providers who will be required to define the technical tools and mechanisms for securing portability across services achieving functional equivalence. Central to the success of future pilots will be the proof of the interoperability standards to provide for the porting of digital assets, the integration of multi-provider environments and the successful achievement of the functional equivalence required for a smooth service transition and competitive market. The developed platforms and systems should demonstrate this portability in practice and work across all verticals to deliver common minimum interoperable requirements that will contribute to the definition of the European open standards.

2. OBLIGATION FOR HIGH RISK AI SYSTEMS

In practice, most of the obligations that are laid out in the proposed AI act refer to the so-called High-Risk AI systems. These include systems¹⁹ which rely on the biometric identification and categorisation of natural personas, as well as systems deployed in the management and operation of critical infrastructure, more precisely, those that are intended to be used as safety components in the management of road traffic and supply of water, gas, heating and electricity.

Any future CEI pilot must be able to ascertain whether it involves the design and deployment of high-risk AI and take measures to ensure compliance is built in at the earliest stage possible by:

- Developing and implementing risk management systems.
- Ensuring training, validating and testing data sets are subject to appropriate data governance and management practices.
- Drawing up the required technical documentation.

¹⁸ Defined in article 3(2)

¹⁹ The full list of High-risk AI systems in article 6(2) of the AI Aact can be found in Annex III.

- Establishing appropriate record-keeping measures, including event logs.
- Designing systems that afford the greatest transparency to users, enable human oversight and provide clarity on expected lifetime and maintenance.
- Developing them in a way that ensures accuracy, robustness through technical redundancy or other measures and address cybersecurity measures designed to prevent data poisoning or model flaws.

A Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach to the deployment of intelligence products and services should be considered, which brings the consumer into an active and prosumer role which provides user agency within the defined high-risk circumstances that they will come into contact with the solution. The pilots will provide a controlled environment for this but should establish a common European playbook and tools for the development of the consumer awareness which is a template for other AI providers, importers, and distributors.

3. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES BEHIND COMPLIANCE-BY-DEFAULT

Data spaces and smart contracts which meet the compliance characteristics must be seen as the key enablers and be integrated into the architectures and activities of the pilots that provides the interface security and control for a scaled access to data by users with automated mechanisms that are trialled and adopted within industry to reduce the burden on device manufacturers and support the user acceptance.

Supporting a future-proof CEI

1. VOLUNTARY CEI CODES OF CONDUCT

The proposed AI Act provides for voluntary codes of conduct that may be drawn up individual providers of AI systems or by organisations representing them with the involvement of users and stakeholders. There is an opportunity for future CSAs to support this process within and between different CEI communities.

2. CE MARKING FOR FUTURE SCALING

Specific support will be required for the development of self-assessment criteria for risk of AI products and the categorisation with a common tool for facilitating compliance-by-default mechanism as well as coordinating the contributions towards the relevant codes of conduct. Related to this would be the requirement for all developed solutions to achieve the CE mark with a structured process collaboratively produced alongside the pilot actors and experienced actors from the market surveillance sphere.

3. STANDARDISATION FOR COMPLIANCE AND COMPETENCE OF DATA

Across the Data Spaces operation, smart contract development and cloud interoperability, a robust mechanism should be put in place to enable the development of European standards by the competent authorities and relevant SDOs. Similar to the CE marking of the AI solutions, a recognisable compliance marking for smart contracts, automated data access interfaces and data spaces operations could support the attraction of industry who will be seeking clarity and guidance on the practical challenges they will face. An outward-facing interface with industry should be considered that treats the pilots as an experimental factory and is able to distil world-leading guidance for external guidance to realise the vision for the European technology ecosystem.

4. A COLLABORATIVE AND ACTIVE REGULATOR

There exists a role for the participation of previously non-traditional actors in the activities of the pilots, specifically involving regulatory bodies and other public bodies who should be considered as key stakeholders and direct participants in the CEI community. Both regulators and public emergency bodies will have elevated and direct roles in the demonstrated platforms, solutions and a significant interest in the outcomes which will reduce disruption for industry adoption of new obligations.

A regulatory sandbox created around the high-risk AI solutions to be developed will enable the upskilling of all stakeholders with managed learnings that will make solutions market-ready from the start and provide the dialogue between market regulators and tech developers which is a new ground outside of the Fintech sector.

Public agencies can also leverage the platforms in developing their own data capacities and technologies and acting as trials for future public interest tasks and examples of exceptional need.